

Conceptions of Rural Education: a systematic literature review

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ABSTRACT. This study aims to analyze the concepts of rural education present in scientific articles published in Scielo database and in *Revista Brasileira de Educação do Campo*, from 2016 to 2021. Therefore, we have used a systematic literature review in a qualitative meta-analysis typology and, based on the review protocol, we have performed searches with the descriptors "rural education", "conception" and "rural school". After mapping the productions, reading the titles, keywords and abstracts, applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, thirteen (13) works were selected and analyzed in that study to answer the question: what are the conceptions of rural education present in scientific articles published in Scielo database and in *Revista Brasileira de Educação do Campo* – Brazilian Journal of Rural Education, from 2016 to 2021? The research has showed that the evaluated works present a conception of rural education from the perspective of law, the result of struggles of peasant social movements. It has also showed that only 5.67% of the articles published in the selected databases on the subject of rural education debate the issue of conceptions.

Keywords: rural education, conceptions, rural school.

Concepções de Educação do Campo: uma revisão sistemática de literatura

RESUMO. Este estudo tem como objetivo analisar as concepções de Educação do Campo presentes em artigos científicos publicados na base do Scielo e na Revista Brasileira de Educação do Campo no período de 2016 a 2021. Para tanto, utilizamos a revisão sistemática de literatura na tipologia meta-análise qualitativa e, a partir do protocolo de revisão, realizamos as buscas com os descritores “educação do campo”, “concepção” e “escola do campo”. Após o mapeamento das produções, leitura dos títulos, palavras-chaves e dos resumos, aplicando os critérios de inclusão e exclusão, foram selecionadas e analisadas nesse estudo treze (13) obras para responder à questão de pesquisa: quais as concepções de Educação do Campo presentes em artigos científicos publicados na base do Scielo e na Revista Brasileira de Educação do Campo no período de 2016 a 2021? A pesquisa evidenciou que as obras avaliadas apresentam uma concepção de Educação do Campo na perspectiva do direito, fruto das lutas dos movimentos sociais camponeses. Evidenciou ainda que apenas 5,67% dos artigos publicados nas bases selecionadas sobre o tema Educação do Campo debatem a questão das concepções.

Palavras-chave: educação do campo, concepções, escola do campo.

Concepciones de Educación Rural: una revisión sistemática de la literatura

RESUMEN. Este estudio tiene como objetivo analizar los conceptos de educación rural presentes en artículos científicos publicados en la base de datos Scielo y en la Revista Brasileira de Educação do Campo, de 2016 a 2021. Por lo tanto, utilizamos una revisión sistemática de la literatura en una tipología de metaanálisis cualitativo y, con base en el protocolo de revisión, realizamos búsquedas con los descriptores "educación agrícola", "concepción" y "escuela rural". Luego de mapear las producciones, leer los títulos, palabras clave y resúmenes, aplicando los criterios de inclusión y exclusión, se seleccionaron y analizaron trece (13) trabajos en este estudio para dar respuesta a la pregunta de investigación: ¿Cuáles son las concepciones de Educación Rural presentes en los artículos científicos publicados, en la base de datos Scielo y en la Revista Brasileira de Educação do Campo, de 2016 a 2021? La investigación mostró que los trabajos evaluados presentan una concepción de la Educación Rural desde la perspectiva del derecho, resultado de las luchas de los movimientos sociales campesinos. También mostró que solo el 5.67% de los artículos publicados en las bases de datos seleccionadas sobre el tema de Educación Rural debaten el tema de las concepciones.

Palabras clave: educación rural, concepciones, escuela rural.

Introduction

Rural Education has constituted as an educational policy of great relevance to guarantee rural individuals the right to access knowledge historically produced and worked on by school institutions. In that context, discussing conceptions of Rural Education demands knowing the historical struggles organized by social movements which have culminated in policies and guidelines for education systems to meet the educational demands of rural populations in Brazil, considering the specificities of those subjects.

As a phenomenon of the current Brazilian reality led by peasant workers and their organizations, Rural Education aims to influence the country educational policy, based on interests, social struggles, work, culture and knowledge of peasant individuals, with implications for field and society project, Caldart (2012). That conception highlights the protagonists of rural education and its fundamental characteristic of linking the interests of peasant populations. In this sense, when conceptualizing that type of teaching, Caldart (2012) points out it is not restricted to the provision of schools in the countryside, but, especially, an educational policy based on an integral development project for the countryside with its social individuals.

Scholars and researchers of this type of teaching point out conceptual differences that exist between Rural Education and Field Education. The fundamental characteristic in distancing these concepts lies in the liberating and emancipatory vision on which Rural Education is based, recognizing the peasant population as social subjects of law and producers of knowledge. From that perspective, Caldart (2011, p. 155) states that “... this educational project reaffirms and dialogues with the pedagogy of the oppressed in its insistence that the oppressed are the subjects of their own education, of their liberation”. Thus, Rural Education represents an advance for the idea of Field Education due to its commitment to the subjects of its educational action.

Field Education is characterized by its disengagement from the subjects it is intended for and the communities in which it is inserted. Likewise, pedagogical practices developed in rural schools were of questionable quality and served for submission, obedience and contrary interests to rural peoples. In this way, this educational project is based on economic and ideological objectives of a dominant class in the country and is at the service of a project of society sustained by subjugation and exploitation of the countryside and the subjects that inhabit it (Santos, 2012; 2018).

The points discussed indicate that those two educational projects, despite being aimed at the peasant population, present fundamental issues that distance them, divergent and even conflicting points. Therefore, it is necessary to know and debate the specific points of each one, in order to understand the pedagogical projects that are developed in schools that serve the subjects of the countryside.

Considering those reflections, this systematic literature review article begins with a question: what are the concepts of Rural Education present in scientific articles published in Scielo database and in *Revista Brasileira de Educação do Campo* (Brazilian Journal of Rural Education), in the period from 2016 to 2021? Such questioning dialogues with the master's research developed in the Postgraduate Program in Teaching at the State University of Southwest Bahia (PPGEn/UESB), which has as its locus of investigation a school in the municipality, called rural school. In that sense, our motivations are anchored, both in the interest in understanding Rural Education, its pedagogical implications in rural schools; as well as dialogue with our education, research area and professional performance.

In line with our research question, we have established the objective of this investigation to analyze the concepts of rural education present in scientific articles published in Scielo database and in *Revista Brasileira de Educação do Campo*, from 2016 to 2021. In all stages of this scientific investigation, 13 (thirteen) works were selected that constituted our primary data that, after analysis and discussions, contributed to the resolution of the research question and produced conclusions, albeit provisional.

With a view to a better systematization of the elements to be addressed we have organized this article into three sections, the first of which is constituted by this introduction that contextualizes the Rural Education theme, the problem and the objective of the research. In the second section entitled “development”, it contemplates the “methodological aspects of the research” and the “analysis and discussion of results”. Finally, in the third section, we deal with the final considerations, presenting the main evidence resulting from the research work.

Methodological aspects of research

The present investigation is configured as a systematic literature review (SLR), following specific protocols to, from existing productions, answer the research question and

foster new knowledge on the subject in question. From this perspective, SLR is a type of scientific investigation that requires all the procedures of a research.

A systematic literature review is a scientific research composed of its own objectives, research problems, methodology, results and conclusion, not just a mere introduction of a larger research, as may be the case of a review of convenience literature (Galvão & Ricarte 2020, p. 3).

With that perspective and considering the different types of SLR, we have adopted qualitative meta-analysis, which, according to Galvão and Ricarte (2020), is a type of research that aims to summarize qualitative studies and identify themes, concepts or key theories to help in understanding the object of study. Thus, in order to carry out that SLR, in planning phase, we have developed a research protocol, containing: objective, research question, selected databases, search descriptors, inclusion and exclusion criteria of the works and the data analysis strategy .

In our protocol, we have established two databases for the search and selection of articles to be analyzed. Revista Brasileira de Educação do Campo (RBEC), available at: <https://sistemas.uft.edu.br › periodicals> , an electronic periodical of Departamento de Educação do Campo, of Universidade Federal do Tocantins, *campus* of Tocantinópolis; for its relevance with continuous publications of articles, thematic dossiers, essays, interviews and reviews of themes related to rural education, in different areas of national and international research. We have also defined the Scientific Electronic Library Online (SciELO) database, available at <https://www.scielo.br/?lng=pt>, cooperative electronic portal of scientific journals, for its recognition by the academic community and its importance to society, with regard to dissemination of productions in the field of science.

The time frame adopted for the two bases was from January 2016 to May 2021, corresponding to the period of existence of RBEC, covering all editions, from its entry in 2016, until May 2021, the date on which we carried out the searches in the two databases of our research.

In order to identify articles that significantly address the theme and research question, we have established the inclusion and exclusion criteria for scientific productions. Table 01 presents the established criteria.

Table 01 - Inclusion and exclusion criteria.

INCLUSION	EXCLUSION
Articles in Portuguese published in the Revista Brasileira de Educação no Campo from 2016 to 2021 that address Rural Education.	Articles in a foreign language published in the Revista Brasileira de Educação no Campo from 2016 to 2021.
Articles in Portuguese language published in the Scielo database, from 2016 to 2021, using the descriptor Rural Education.	Articles in a foreign language published in the Scielo database, from 2016 to 2021, using the descriptor Rural Education.
Articles that in the title, among the keywords or in the abstract, have had the following descriptors: (1) Rural Education; (2) Conception; (3) Rural School.	Articles that in the title, among the keywords or in the abstract, have not had the following descriptors: (1) Rural Education; (2) Conception; (3) Rural School.
Articles that in the abstract indicated that they would address conceptions of Rural Education.	Articles that in the summary did not indicate that they would address conceptions of Rural Education.

Source - Researchers' production.

In Scielo's database, when selecting the option search by article, by subject and using the descriptor “Rural Education” AND “Conception”, 05 (five) articles were identified. With the descriptors “Rural Education” AND “Rural School” we have not identified any article. With the descriptors “Rural Education” AND “Conception” AND “Rural School” no article was found. With the descriptors “Rural Education” AND “concept” no article was found either. Using only the descriptor “Rural Education”, 62 (sixty-two) articles were found.

Table 02 - Search results on Scielo portal.

DESCRIPTORS	RESULTS FOUND
“Rural Education” AND “Conception”	05
“Rural Education” AND “Rural School”	0
“Rural Education” AND “Conception” AND “Rural School”	0
“Rural Education” AND “concept”	0
“Rural Education”	62

Source - Researchers' production.

Working with 62 (sixty-two) articles, we have applied the time frame from 2016 to 2021, in which 37 (thirty-seven) works were identified, of these, 02 (two) in English, 01 (one) in Spanish and 34 (thirty-four) in Portuguese. When applying the inclusion criteria: articles that in the title, among the keywords or in the abstract had the descriptors: (1) Rural Education; (2) Conception; (3) Rural School, 10 (ten) works were selected. When applying the inclusion criteria, articles that in the abstract indicated that they would address conceptions of Rural Education, 03 (three) articles were selected from the Scielo database.

In RBEC electronic journal, we performed searches from January 2016 to May 2021. During that period, 270 (two hundred and seventy) articles were published, 28 (twenty-eight) in Spanish, 47 (forty-seven) in English and 195 (one hundred and ninety-five) in Portuguese. When applying the inclusion criteria: articles that in the title, among the keywords or in the abstract had the descriptors: (1) Rural Education; (2) Conception; (3) Rural School, 31 (thirty-one) articles were selected. When applying the inclusion criteria; articles that indicated in the abstract that they would address conceptions of Rural Education, 10 (ten) articles were selected. In table 03 we present the refinement of the data based on these criteria.

Table 03: Search results in Brazilian Journal of Rural Education (RBEC).

INCLUSION CRITERIA	RESULTS OBTAINED
Articles in Portuguese from 2016 to 2021 that address Rural Education.	195
Articles that in the title, among the keywords or in the abstract had the following descriptors: (1) Rural Education; (2) Conception; (3) Rural School.	31
Articles that in the abstract indicated that they would address conceptions of Rural Education.	10

Source: Researchers' production.

With the searches carried out in Scielo database and in Revista Brasileira de Educação do Campo, we have obtained 13 (thirteen) articles that constituted the primary data for our research. In table 04 we present the data refinement process, considering the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Table 04 - Refinement of data obtained in selected databases.

INCLUSION CRITERIA	SCIELO	RBEC
Articles in Portuguese language published from 2016 to 2021.	34	195
Articles that, among the keywords or in the abstract, had the following descriptors: (1) Rural Education; (2) Conception; (3) Rural School.	10	31
Articles that in the abstract indicated that they would address conceptions of Rural Education.	03	10

Source: Researchers' production.

Thus, following this methodological path, 13 (thirteen) articles were selected. Finally, all thirteen works were read in full for quality certification, in order to answer our research question. In order to make the identification of articles easier, we have classified them in a sequence from A1 to A13, in which the "A" represents the word "article" and the sequence agreeing with the titles and respective keywords, as shown in table 05.

Table 05 - Title, keywords, year and publication base.

ABBREVIATION OF THE STUDY	TITLE	KEYWORDS	BASE YEAR
A 01	Interfaces between rural schools and social movements in Brazil.	Rural Schools, Social Movements, Rural Education.	2016 RBEC
A 02	Proneira in the Sertão Mineiro Goiano: Reflections on Social Emancipation and Rural Education	Public Policies for Agrarian Reform, Rural Education, Emancipation, Educator Training, Youth and Adult Education.	2016 RBEC
A 03	From Field Education to Rural Education: an epistemological/paradigmatic struggle to overcome	Rural Education, Field Education, Epistemological Paradigms.	2016 RBEC
A 04	Rural education in dispute: Resistance versus subordination to capital.	Paradigms. Disputes. Rural Education. Resistance. Rural Youth Entrepreneurship Program.	2017 Scielo
A 05	School education in rural areas in the municipality of Ituiutaba-MG, Brazil: Field Education or Rural Education?	Field Education, Rural Education, Rural Schools.	2017 RBEC
A 06	Notes on Rural Education in Colorado do Oeste/Rondonia: notes from a literate peasant.	Rural Education, Social Movement, Educational System.	2018 RBEC
A 07	Contemporary portraits of Rural Education: investigative movements in Jiquiriçá Valley-Bahia.	Rural Education, Multiseries Classes, Teacher Training.	2018 RBEC
A 08	Rural Education in the National Education Plan: tensions between guaranteeing and denying the right to education.	Rural Education. National Education Plan. Public policy.	2018 Scielo
A 09	Rural school organization: teachers' conceptions and expectations.	Rural Education Policy, School Organization, School Management.	2019 RBEC
A 10	Rural Family Succession: (Im) Possibilities of School in the Countryside of the Municipality of Barra Bonita (SC).	Educational Policies, Rural Education, Youth, Permanence, Succession.	2020 RBEC
A 11	Rural Education and its specificities: a study of the Political Pedagogical Project of a rural school in the city of Londrina-PR	Rural Education, Political Pedagogical Project, Londrina.	2020 RBEC
A 12	Practice of Rural Education and agrarian paradigms in Geography	Peasant, Rural Education, Agrarian Trend.	2020 RBEC
A 13	Education of rural peoples in Brazil: coloniality/modernity and urbancentrism.	Coloniality; urbancentrism; field education; Rural Education; decoloniality.	2020 Scielo

Source: Researchers' production.

The data in table 05, with the titles, keywords, year and publication base, allow us to visualize that the selected studies present, in the title or in the keywords, the descriptors established in the research. We also emphasize that, among the inclusion or exclusion criteria of works, we have carried out the reading of the abstract to also identify the approach to the conception of rural education. Also in table 05, it is possible to visualize the year of publication and the database in which each work was published. We can see that the time

frame from 2016 to 2021 was observed, despite not having selected any article from the year 2021, as we did not find studies that met the inclusion criteria established in the protocol. We also emphasize that all selected works were located in full in the databases used in this study.

Analysis and discussion of results

After locating and selecting the 13 (thirteen) scientific productions to develop our SRL, we had carried out a careful study of each work to proceed with the analysis and discussion of results. Thus, we seek to identify and analyze the conceptions of Rural Education present in the articles published in Scielo database and in Revista Brasileira de Educação do Campo, from 2016 to 2021.

The first analysis describes the quantity and frequency of publications in the time frame from 2016 to 2021. In table 04, we present a refinement of the data in each selected base. In Scielo database, 34 (thirty-four) articles were published in Portuguese in the period investigated, of which only 03 (three) address the concept of Rural Education; a percentage of only 8.82%. In the database Revista Brasileira de Educação do Campo, 195 (one hundred and ninety-five) articles were published in Portuguese from 2016 to 2021. Of those, only 5.12% discuss the concept of Rural Education. When considering the two researched bases, we have 229 (two hundred and twenty-nine) articles and only 13 (thirteen), corresponding to 5.67%, discuss the concept of Rural Education.

Those data call attention to the absence of a fundamental issue when discussing Rural Education, which are the concepts that guide debates, policies, guidelines and pedagogical practices. Without clarity on that basic point, conceptual and practical mistakes can be made that can influence the implementation of educational policy for rural individuals, as well as historical achievements of peasant social movements.

In table 05, we present the year of publication of each study. When analyzing that, we found the existence of 03 (three) publications in 2016 (23%); 02 (two) publications in 2017 (15.38%); 03 (three) publications in 2018 (23%); 01 (one) publication in 2019 (7.69%) and 04 (four) publications in 2020 (30.76%). We observed a peak in 2020, concentrating 30.76% of the works and no publications in 2021.

We also have a predominance of selected articles from Revista Brasileira de Educação do Campo, in a total of 10 (ten), corresponding to 76.92%. In that regard, we can highlight the

aforementioned base constitutes an important reference in the country when it comes to publications of studies on Rural Education.

The second analysis we make discusses the rural education conceptions presented in the evaluated works. Table 06 contains fragments of the rural education conceptions of the evaluated articles and the main references used by the authors.

Table 06 - Conception of Rural Education and the main references.

ARTICLE	CONCEPTION OF RURAL EDUCATION	MAIN REFERENCES
A 01	...is an achievement of social movements, strengthened in discussions, participation, experiences and cooperation. Through political clashes, essential for educators, students and social movements, the traditional isolation and individualism imposed by neoliberal society is broken (Santos, 2016, p. 38).	Caldart (2000, 2004, 2012) Campos (2015)
A 02	... arises from the struggle of peasant social movements for the right to an educational process that takes into account their specificities and demands. ... link to a project of society and development and social struggles (Freitas, Dansa & Moreira, 2016, p. 208).	Fernandes (2004) Caldart (2012)
A 03	Overcoming the paradigm of field education for rural education is urgent and emerging so that an education of law can be carried out for the subject of law, because throughout history, knowledge of peasants has been silenced and hidden through an education decontextualized, in which the urban overlapped the rural, maintaining control over teaching and learning process (Costa & Cabral, 2016, p. 194).	Caldart (2000, 2004, 2006, 2008, 2009, 2010, 2012)
A 04	Element of resistance to assist in the struggle for/on land, in order to enable the reproduction of the peasantry as a way of life and a social class... Rural Education must be understood, in contradiction of <i>class struggle</i> , as a strategy of struggle of social movements, aiming at <i>emancipation</i> , as human formation, <i>conflictive</i> , because the field is in conflict (Camacho, 2017, p. 657).	Camacho (2014) Michelloti (2010) Caldart (2005)
A 05	... some quality education in and of the rural, must be understood as an education that promotes actions and strategies for emancipation and citizenship of all individuals that live in the countryside. An education that contributes to training of children, young people and adults for sustainable regional and national development (Júnior & Leite, 2017, p. 332).	Arroyo (2004, 2007) Caldart (2004) Molina (2004) Leite (1999)
A 06	...covers all this cultural diversity, which can be characterized as a movement constituted by social subjects that integrate peasant realities, and that aim to link the process of life in the countryside with educational assumptions, thus combining school and life, the assumptions of peasant daily life and formal educational methods (Souza et al., 2018, p. 316).	Caldart (2012) Cerioli (2002) Kolling (2002) Kolling, Nery e Molina(1999)
A 07	...a contemporary reality that constitutes a right of rural peoples, a Brazilian historical and social debt.... A paradigm under construction, characterized by encompassing all rural spaces (Santos et al., 2018, p. 208).	Caldart (2002; 2004), Fernandes (2012), Pires (2012), Ribeiro (2012),
A 08	Education culturally and socially identified with the territory that workers recognize as a rural (Santos, 2018, p. 194).	Caldart, Molina, Kolling (2012)
A 09	Human right presupposes the struggle for the establishment of solid and effective State policies in line with what has already established in the Federal Constitution of 1988. ... school education that has as its starting point the interests and needs of workers who live in rural	Arroyo (2007) Caldart (2004, 2008)

	areas (Garske Castilho & Cândido, 2019, p. 05).	
A 10	Rural education meets the rural subjects, the identity of the place in which it is inserted and is organized with the participation of those who attend it, while the rural school is "given" to the subjects who live in the rural area. (Bernardi & Kuhn, 2020, p. 06).	Fernandes, Cerioli e Caldart (2011)
A 11	Rural education, however, cannot be separated from a development project of and in the field. ... it is necessary to consider the history of the peasant people, who over the years have been exploited and expelled from the countryside, due to a model of capitalist agriculture (Lança & Fernandes, 2020, p. 7).	Caldart (2003, 2012)
A 12	The theoretical-methodological assumptions of rural education are based on educational action of the collective, listening to those who that education interests, building with them, learning with them. An education with class content and commitment, as an instrument for liberation of the oppressed or subaltern class (Assunção, 2020, p. 20).	Caldart (2004, 2010, 2015) Arroyo (1989) Molina (2008) Munarim (2008) Souza (2008) Freire (1983)
A 13	...an insurgent movement that, in addition to enunciating alternative epistemologies, has its origins in decolonial movements, fundamental in rural social movements and in paths of popular education. ... one of the movements that point to that construction of a Brazilian education and society, based on <i>what peoples really are</i> , overcoming social representations based on inferiority, articulating with other movements that are in that perspective, such as the Black Movement, Feminist, LGBTTT9, from urban peripheries, among others (Farias & Faleiro, 2020, p. 16).	Caldart (2012)

Source: Researchers' production.

When reflecting on the concept of rural education, presented in each work, it is possible to identify convergences around several aspects. The first aspect that we highlight is the understanding of rural education from the perspective of law. When the authors punctuate education as a right, they also point out that right is the result of struggles of peasant social movements, in search of constitutional guarantees for education. In that sense, they call attention that this “Human right presupposes the struggle for the establishment of solid and effective State policies in line with what has already been established in the Federal Constitution of 1988” (Garske, Castilho & Cândido, 2019, p. 05). It is important to highlight that in this aspect we have a fundamental element that differentiates rural education from field education, which is the insertion, through struggles, of rural subjects in public educational policies in our country.

The insertion of Rural Education in the country's political agenda has culminated in important educational guidelines for this type of education, such as Operational Guidelines for Basic Education in Rural Schools, Resolution CNE/CEB nº 1 of 2002 and Resolution CNE/CEB nº 2 of 2008. For Fernandes (2011, p. 144), those guidelines represent an advance and, “knowing this history of struggle that makes the law, we also know that the struggle makes the law enforce. For that reason, without the organization of rural people, guidelines

run the risk of being forgotten in planning”. The author highlights the importance of striving not only for the establishment of the law, but, above all, that it becomes effective.

The second converging aspect in relation to the concept of rural education concerns the link with the concrete life of the subjects, an education oriented to their specificities, which configures an education in and of the countryside. Based on Caldart (2011, p. 150), in the countryside because “the people have the right to be educated in the place where they live” and in the countryside, because “the people have the right to an education designed from their place and with their participation, linked to their culture and their human and social needs”. For the same purpose, in article A10, the authors argue: “Rural education meets the rural subjects, the identity of the place in which it is inserted and is organized with the participation of those who attend it, while the rural school is “given” to subjects living in rural areas” (Bernardi & Kuhn, 2020, p. 06). In that fragment, the authors highlight another element of distance between rural education and field education, which is their link to the subjects of their educational action.

This fundamental principle of rural education is established in the 2002 Operational Guidelines, approved by National Education Council. In his second article, we find an approach to the identity of a rural school.

The identity of rural school is defined by its connection to issues inherent to its reality, anchored in the temporality and knowledge of students, in collective memory that signals futures, in network of science and technology available in society and in social movements in defense of projects that associate solutions required by those issues to the social quality of collective life in the country (Brasil, 2002).

As established in guidelines, and in line with article A06, a school, within the principles of rural education, must “link the process of life in the countryside with the educational assumptions, thus combining school and life, the assumptions of peasant and everyday life and formal educational methods” (Souza et al., 2018, p. 316). Here too, we can identify a gap between the rural school and the field school, designed and organized in urban molds.

The third converging aspect in the evaluated articles, in relation to the concept of rural education, concerns its link to a project of society. In that sense, the construction of a new social reality demands that “break with the traditional isolation and individualism imposed by neoliberal society” (Santos, 2016, p. 38). And yet, “an educational process that takes into account their specificities and demands. ... link to a project of society and development and to social struggles” (Freitas, Dansa & Moreira, 2016, p. 207). From that point of view, education is constituted as a social practice in which the struggle for the constitutional right to

knowledge must be articulated with other social struggles, within a society project, supported by principles such as inclusion, dialogue and diversity, “overcoming social representations based on inferiority” of rural subjects (Farias & Faleiro, 2020, p. 16). Also in that aspect, we note a distance from field education, structured in ideological and economic interests contrary to the rural population.

The data presented in table 06 also highlight an important element in the conceptions of rural education present in 13 (thirteen) articles investigated in this systematic literature review. In the selected reference, we noticed the recurrence of the author Roseli Salette Caldart in all the evaluated works. In that case, we have found a harmony in the works, with regard to the search for the same reference to discuss the concept of rural education which, according to Caldart (2012, p. 257) “... names a phenomenon of the current Brazilian reality, carried out by rural workers and their organizations, which aims to influence education policy from the social interests of peasant communities”. This author's definition converges with the conceptions identified in the evaluated articles and diverges, in several aspects, from the idea of field education.

The third analysis will discuss the concept of field education, as we consider it important since it is often used as a synonym for rural education, or even, the convergent and divergent aspects existing in these categories of analysis of reality called education are questioned. Furthermore, the authors of the evaluated works also referred to these aforementioned discussions to discuss, in their articles, the concept of rural education.

In table 07 we find fragments of rural education concepts presented in the articles evaluated in our SLR.

Table 07 - Conception of Rural Education.

ARTICLE	RURAL EDUCATION
A 01	... the struggle for survival, individual and collective, breaks with the various faces of the judiciary, police and media. It also breaks with field education, which is traditional and conservative (Santos, 2016, p. 41).
A 02	... often worked from the perspective of importing an urban model to the countryside, which did nothing more than encourage part of that population to leave the countryside or school. Part of that urban teaching started to reinforce the disqualification of the peasant, representing the countryside, in the popular imagination, as a place of backwardness in relation to the new capitalist industrial system that was implanted, stimulating the rural exodus, of women and, especially, of youth (Freitas, Dansa & Moreira, 2016, p. 208).
A 03	... the education proposed to rural subjects constitutes a form of exclusion and oppression, since it brings the principles of hegemony, naturalizing these and imposing knowledge that has nothing to do with their culture. They do not include peasants in the condition of protagonists, thus, leaving them excluded from an educational process that aims at human formation, having this only as an extension of the education proposed to the urban population, aiming at the formation of human capital (Costa & Cabral, 2016, p. 193).

A 04	In the agricultural capital (ACP) paradigm, the concept of rural education is appropriated by NGOs/institutes with the financing of companies and serving agribusiness and young people must be prepared to compete in the market (Camacho, 2017).
A 05	... the city was idealized as a civilizing space, an expression of political, cultural and educational dynamics. As a result, the urban paradigm became the inspiration for the right to education (Júnior & Leite, 2017, p. 328)
A 06	Rural education is an advance for the idea of field education, because this idea is not limited to bringing education, it needs to be literally in contact with the workers it is intended for (Souza et al., 2018, p. 317)
A 07	Field education “privileged the state of domination of agrarian elites over workers, mainly to establish harmony and order in cities and increase rural productivity” (Pires, 2012, p. 81). <i>Pedagogical Ruralism</i> , an educational movement characterized by the ideal of keeping the rural population in the countryside, seeking to avoid the migration of large numbers of people to urban centers (Santos et al., 2018 p. 210)
A 08	It is possible to identify the prioritization, in general, on the part of field education, of meeting the demands created by the internal and external markets, to the detriment of guaranteeing the schooling of men and women in the countryside, which can be recognized in three different moments discussed below (Santos, p. 188).
A 09	... training aimed at accepting the model created for urban schools (Garske, Castilho & Cândido, 2019, p. 04).
A 10	... rural education differs from field education or what takes place in the countryside due to the meaning of its educational practices (Bernardi & Kuhn, 2020, p. 06).
A 11	... there was a field education, but without this education valuing in the countryside the less favored classes and the subjects that represent them. Education for the countryside was linked to development of the country so that the agrarian elite could exercise control over rural people (Lança & Fernandes, 2020, p. 12).
A 12	... develops as a continuation of urban education, decontextualized, encouraging the evasion of young people, by presenting a vision of archaic and backward rural and not as a reflection of the history of abandonment to which the Brazilian countryside was denied in these 520 years of existence of Brazil (Assunção, 2020, p. 13).
A 13	... was linked to interests of elite and agrarian oligarchies, under a project that tended to intensify the submission of work to capital, opposing the formulation of education as a process of liberation from oppressive relations of peasants. In that way, field education is at the service of market and economy, and, thus, of coloniality of subjects of the countryside, offering an education solely along these lines, annulling their conditions of existence, their struggles and their ways of life, giving the these alienating functions and education to generate labor for subjection to capitalism (Farias & Faleiro, 2020, p. 14).

Source: Production of researchers.

In the article A 08 “Rural Education in the National Education Plan: tensions between guaranteeing and denying the right to education”, Santos discusses field education, the converging and divergent aspects in relation to rural education, a perspective assumed by the author. For Santos (2018, p. 188), “It is possible to identify the prioritization, in general, on the part of field education, of meeting the demands created by the internal and external markets, to the detriment of guaranteeing the education of man and woman of the country”. That conception presents a fundamental trait that distances field education from rural education. The first meets the interests of the market, working in training of labor and consumers, and the second meets the interests of subjects of its educational action, committing to their struggles and to a project of society based on emancipation and social transformation.

In line with those reflections, in the article A 13 “Education of rural peoples in Brazil: coloniality/modernity and urbancentrism” Farias and Faleiro, based on Latin American decolonial studies, discuss the school process in Brazil with attention to education of rural people. According to the authors, coloniality directly affects rural subjects, as their territories are considered as spaces at the service of capital, agribusiness and school is placed at the service of this complex structure of colonization. In that context, field education, "... was linked to the interests of elite and agrarian oligarchies, under a project that tended to intensify the submission of work to capital, opposing the formulation of education as a process of liberation from the oppressive relations of peasants” (Farias & Faleiro, 2020, p. 14). In this line of discussion, Freitas, Dansa and Moreita (2016), in article A 02, argue that model of education directly contributed to stimulating the rural exodus, encouraging the population to leave the countryside for the city.

In this reflection, we can still identify other divergent aspects between rural education and field education. While the first recognizes the specificities of peasant subjects, their life trajectories and their social and cultural protagonism, the second is structured in the subordination, subjugation and inferiorization of those people in the educational action.

In the debate presented in the articles evaluated in that SLR about the two models of education for rural people, we can identify a harmony in the authors' arguments, which allows the reader to understand the main characteristics of each model and its implications for educational policies, guidelines and practices. In this perspective, when discussing the concepts of education, it is also essential to debate the paradigm of field education that can still influence and be present in schools and in their educational practices.

The fourth and last aspect to be analyzed in this SLR refers to objectives, keywords and methodology established by the authors in their articles. We seek to identify and analyze, among the objectives and keywords, the way in which the category “social movements” and the category “public policies” of rural education appear. In the latter, we consider: rural school, teacher training, political-pedagogical project, PRONERA, National Education Plan. This analysis is important, as it reflects two fundamental moments of this teaching modality: its gestation in social movements and its institution as a public educational policy.

Table 08 - Objectives and keywords.

ARTICLE	OBJETIVE	KEYWORDS
A 01	To present reflections on the critical production of knowledge, linked to the principles of rural education and the counter-hegemonic values defended by social movements.	Rural Schools, Social Movements, Rural Education.

A 02	Reflect on rural education, as a result of struggles of social movements, for the right of rural subjects to think about education and production from the place where they live, with human emancipation as a horizon; and, the complexity of training educators in adult education.	Public Policies for Agrarian Reform, Rural Education, Emancipation, Educator Training, Youth and Adult Education.
A 03	It investigates, from a theoretical, interpretative and critical perspective, the conceptions of field education and rural education in the struggle for epistemological overcoming, with emphasis on the educational paradigms postulated by social movements, characterizing them and reflecting on the proposals presented in the conceptual overcoming of reality of rural education.	Rural Education, Field Education, Epistemological Paradigms.
A 04	Demonstrate the existing paradigmatic differences between rural education built from the peasant tendency of the Agrarian Question Paradigm (AQP) and the rural education proposal built from the Agrarian Capitalism Paradigm (ACP).	Paradigms. Disputes. Rural Education. Resistance. Rural Youth Entrepreneurship Program.
A 05	To present some reflections on the history of education carried out in the Brazilian countryside, prioritizing the differentiation between the paradigm of field education and the paradigm of rural education; to map the academic production that deals with the investigated theme and, finally, to take a look at the investigation scenario: the municipality of Ituiutaba-Minas Gerais, Brazil.	Field Education, Rural Education, Rural Schools.
A 06	Addressing concerns about the existing dichotomy between education in the countryside and rural education.	Rural Education, Social Movement, Educational System.
A 07	Expand studies and promote debates on rural education in the territory of Vale do Jiquiriçá.	Rural Education, Multigrade Classes, Teacher Training.
A 08	To reflect on the way in which the debate of rural education appears in the documents analyzed, explaining tensions that emerge from the current plan, which oscillates between guaranteeing and not realizing the right to education. In addition, it problematizes the concept of field education and takes the perspective of rural education in the reflection of legal texts.	Rural education. National Education Plan. Public policy.
A 09	To analyze conceptions and expectations of teachers in relation to organization of rural school.	Rural Education Policy, School Organization, School Management.
A 10	Understand whether public policies aimed at rural education promote the permanence/succession of young people on rural properties.	Educational Policies, Rural Education, Youth, Permanence, Succession.
A 11	To present aspects of rural education, understanding its peculiarities and correlating them to the political pedagogical project of a rural school, revealing what is established (or not) as purposes of a peasant pedagogical practice.	Rural Education, Political Pedagogical Project, Londrina.
A 12	To establish the relationship between the theoretical conceptions of paradigms of agrarian studies and rural education, in order to defend an education consistent with the needs of rural men and women and their children, which values their way of life, strengthens their political organization-economic, producing knowledge that improves the quality of life in the countryside.	Peasant, Rural Education, Agrarian Tendency.
A 13	To analyze the processes of coloniality/modernity and urbancentrism as categories that explain the subalternization of rural people, highlighting the historical constitution of Brazilian formal education.	Coloniality; Urbancentrism; Field Education; Rural Education; Decoloniality.

Source: Production of researchers.

The analysis of objectives and keywords from the categories "social movements" and "public policies" indicates that the studies evaluated, when discussing Rural Education, consider their original constitution from the struggles of social movements in search for public policies educational programs in line with their needs and interests. Thus, Souza (2008, p. 1098), argues that "rural education expresses the ideology and strength of social movements, in search for a public education that values the identity and culture of rural peoples". From that perspective, when discussing conceptions, the presence of those constitutive and identity elements of rural education is essential.

By analyzing the category "public policies", considering the terms of this axis, we can identify its presence in most of the studies evaluated. More often we have "rural school" and "public policies" with three records each, "teacher training" appears with two records. It is important to highlight that of the 13 (thirteen) works evaluated, 08 (eight) present the category "public policies", corresponding to 61.50%.

By analyzing the recurrence of the term "public policy" and "social movements", we can think of an evolutionary trajectory of the disciplinary field under analysis. In that line of reflection, we can recognize this teaching modality consolidating itself as a public educational policy in our country. However, it is still necessary to consider that this countryside in dispute, which is configured as rural education, cannot be disconnected from the original framework that has generated it, despite the current scenario, the establishment of conflicting forces in a process of delegitimization of social movements and even their criminalization.

It is important to highlight that, there is a predominance of qualitative research approach in the works, with the use of various data collection techniques such as conversation circles, focus groups, semi-structured interviews, participant observation, document analysis, questionnaires, among others. In that sense, we note researchers, for the most part, seek to verify their research problems, observing how they manifest themselves in the daily life of institutions, with a predominance of educational institutions.

Final considerations

As rural education is a phenomenon of the current Brazilian reality that has as its original protagonist rural workers and their organizations. Considering also it presents a concept under construction and constitutes a field in dispute, promoting research and discussions around the object of study "conceptions of rural education", it is configured as a

strategic action in consolidation of this field of knowledge, with theoretical impacts and practical.

Based on those reflections, on the investigative process developed and on results achieved, we can conclude that the objective of analyzing the conceptions of rural education present in scientific articles published in Scielo database and in *Revista Brasileira de Educação do Campo*, from 2016 to 2021, was reached by the current study.

Based on that investigation, it was possible to identify that only 5.67% of the scientific productions published in the Scielo and RBEC databases on rural education discuss the concepts. In this way, we realize that our object of study is a fertile field for further research, because although we have found works with relevant discussions, allowing for an in-depth analysis of the theme, the low percentage in the set of scientific publications is remarkable. From this gap, new research can be developed, so that the scientific advancement of the area is consolidated and generates benefits for society in general, and particularly for the subjects of rural education.

Based on the discussions presented, it is possible to identify a conception of rural education from the perspective of law and public responsibility, based on the specificities of subjects served by this type of education, the result of struggles of peasant social movements and promoting the emancipation of people and social transformation. Likewise, we can understand it as a critique of field education, structured in urban-centric models, with a view of inferiority and subjugation of the countryside and the subjects that inhabit it.

From this perspective, these educational projects are divergent and serve different interests. Rural education is committed to the subjects of its educational action, their liberation and protagonism, and field education is connected to interests of capital and agribusiness.

Considering those reflections and highlighting the relevance of investigating, discussing and understanding the concepts of rural education, present in scientific productions, and also in the educational practices, developed in rural schools, we point out that research aimed at understanding this theme is extremely relevant for the academy and for society, especially when considering the current scenario in Brazil, more particularly, the educational policies and programs aimed at serving peasant subjects. In view of that, there are gaps to be filled with new research, which deals with the conceptions of rural education from theoretical bases and its implications for educational practices.

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